

EFFECT OF INHIBITORY EXTRACTS OF ENDOPHYTES *ASPERGILLUS FISCHERI VOIR* AND *FUSARIUM SP.-AL142R* ON THE KINETIC CHARACTERISTICS OF PANCREATIC LIPASE

¹Gulyamova T.G., ²Ruziyeva D.M., ³Khasanov X.T., ⁴Yuldosheva M.M., ⁵Abdulmyanova L.I., ⁶Rasulova G.A.

^{1,2,5,6}Institute of Microbiology Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan

³Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology

⁴Alfraganus University

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Abstract. This article presents the results of studying the effect of extracts of endophytic fungi *Aspergillus fischeri VOIR*, isolated from the root of *Viola odorata* and *Fusarium sp.-AL142R*, isolated from the root of *Allium longicuspis* Regel, on the kinetic characteristics of pancreatic lipase. The extracts of these endophytes have the ability to suppress pancreatic lipase activity by 91.5% and 88.5%, respectively, with IC₅₀ values of 20.5 and 20.7 µg/mL, which is comparable to the IC₅₀ of the xenical standard (20.6 µg/mL). The *A.fischeri VOIR* extract was shown to reduce the maximum reaction rate (V_{max}) by 4-fold to 0.005 mg/min compared to 0.02 mg/min without inhibitor. Meanwhile, the K_m value both in the presence and absence of the inhibitor remains unchanged at 10 mg/mL. These data indicate a non-competitive mechanism of action of the inhibitor extract of *A.fischeri VOIR*, since it does not reduce the affinity of lipase for the substrate.

In the presence of the inhibitor extract of *Fusarium sp.-AL142R*, as well as Xenical, the value of K_m (16 mg/ml) increases 1.5-fold, Xenical under experimental conditions increases K_m almost 2.5-fold (25.0 mg/ml), while V_{max} remains at the control level.

The data obtained allow us to conclude that the inhibitor compounds of the endophyte *A.fischeri VOIR* act non-competitively, whereas lipase inhibitors from *Fusarium sp.-AL142R* and Xenical exhibit a competitive type of inhibition.

Keywords: endophytic fungi, pancreatic lipase inhibitors, kinetic characteristics.

Introduction

Obesity is one of the most common diseases worldwide. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), the prevalence of obesity has increased significantly in recent decades and the condition now affects millions of people worldwide [1,2]. Being one of the most common diseases, obesity is a problem that can lead to the development of various diseases such as dyslipidemia, insulin resistance and diabetes, metabolic syndrome, hypertension and increased risk of cardiovascular mortality, some cancers [3]. One of the most effective therapeutic approaches to prevent obesity is to slow down fatty acid absorption by inhibiting pancreatic lipase in the digestive tract [4]. PL inhibitors affect the activity of pancreatic lipase. They are among the peripherally acting drugs that mediate direct reduction of calorie absorption in the gastrointestinal tract and affect lipid absorption [5,6].

The only drug against obesity of this type approved for long-term use is the lipase inhibitor orlistat [7]. However, despite its efficacy, clinical use of orlistat is associated with mild to moderate

gastrointestinal side effects. Therefore, ongoing research is focused on the study and development of novel pancreatic lipase inhibitors that have an improved safety profile and reduced side effects for obese individuals [8]. In recent years, secondary metabolites of endophytic fungi have attracted much attention in drug development for the treatment of various types of health problems [9,10]. Endophytes contribute a lot to the drug discovery and development process because they produce many natural products with novel chemical structures and biological activities [11]. In this aspect, the ability of endophytes to produce secondary metabolites with inhibitory properties to a number of therapeutically important enzymes, including pancreatic lipase, has attracted particular attention [10,11]. Thus, screening of 122 endophytic fungal isolates isolated from 15 plants growing in Uzbekistan revealed the presence of inhibitory activity in 70% of the studied endophytic fungi [12]. Ethyl acetate extracts of biomass of 7 endophytes showed inhibitory activity of 80.8 - 91.5 %, four strains showed activity in the range of 65.8 - 79.9 %. *A.fischeri VOIR* isolated from the root of *Viola odorata* and *Fusarium sp.-AL142R* from the root of *Allium longicuspis Regel* had the highest inhibitory activity, with 91.5% and 88.5% activity, respectively, inhibiting pancreatic lipase activity to the greatest extent under *in vitro* conditions and with IC₅₀ values similar to those of Xenical as a standard inhibitor of 20.0 and 20.7 µg/ml. Therefore, the aim of the present work was to study the effect of ethyl acetate extracts of *A.fischeri VOIR* and *Fusarium sp.-AL142R* on the kinetic characteristics of lipase activity.

Materials and methods of research

Objects of research

Endophytic fungi *A.fischeri VOIR*, isolated from the root of *Viola odorata*, and *Fusarium sp.-AL142R* from the root of *Allium longicuspis Regel*, collected on the territory of Tashkent region served as the object of research.

Cultivation of endophytic fungi isolates

The isolated endophytes were cultured by deep fermentation (DF) on Chapek-Dox medium on a rocker at 180 rpm, temperature 28⁰C for 5 days in 0.5 dm³ and 1 dm³ Erlenmeyer flasks. The nutrient medium was inoculated with either spore or mycelial inoculum. In order to obtain a spore suspension, the fully sporulated culture was washed off the agar jamb with Chapek-Dox medium with saline solution containing 2% Tween-20 and brought to a spore concentration of 1x10⁷ per ml using a Goryaev chamber. Seeding with spore inoculum was carried out at the rate of 5% inoculum of the volume of the culture medium. To obtain mycelial inoculum, flasks with 50 ml of Chapek-Dox medium were inoculated with a suspension of 1x10⁷ spores/ml and cultured on a rocker at 180 rpm, 28⁰C for 3 days. Seeding with mycelial inoculum was also carried out at the rate of 5% inoculum from the volume of culture medium. The grown biomass of cultures was separated by centrifugation at 6 thousand rpm and stored at -4⁰C.

Extraction of secondary metabolites from biomass

Secondary metabolites were extracted from the biomass of endophytic fungi according to Hazalin's method [13]. For this purpose, 5 g of biomass was homogenized in a Potter homogenizer, transferred to a conical flask containing 50 ml of acetic acid ethyl ester and left on a rocker at room temperature for 24 hours for stirring. The mixture was then filtered through a paper filter (absorbent cotton paper #1) and Na₂SO₄ was added at a rate of 40 µg/mL to remove the aqueous layer. The mixture was then evaporated to dryness on a rotary evaporator and 1 ml of dimethyl sulfoxide was added. The obtained extract was used as a mother liquor and stored at +4⁰C.

Determination of inhibition of PL activity

50 mg of lipase ("Sigma", 100 units/mL) was suspended in 10 ml of Tris-NaCl buffer containing 2.5 mM Tris and 2.5 mM NaCl, pH 7.4. The solution was shaken vigorously for 15 min and centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 10 min and the supernatant was collected. Stock solutions of the extracts and Xenical were prepared in DMSO with linear concentrations ranging from 1.56-2000 µg/mL or 0.78-1000 µg/mL. The final reaction mixture consisted of 875 µL of buffer, 100 µL of enzyme and 20 µL of extract at different initial concentration pre-incubated for 5 min at 37 °C followed by addition of 10 µL of substrate (4-nitrophenylpalmitate in 10 mM in acetonitrile) incubated at 37°C for one hour for incubation. The amount of DMSO in the final concentration did not exceed 2%. The optical mixture was measured on a spectrophotometer (UV-vis model UV-5100) after 5 minutes at 405 nm [14]. The percentage of inhibition was calculated according to the formula:

$$\% \text{ inhibition} = [(Ae - At) / Ae] \times 100$$

where Ae is the optical density of the enzyme control (without inhibitor) and the difference between the optical density of the test sample with and without substrate. A linear regression equation was constructed to establish the correlation between the logarithm of the concentration of the test substances and the percentage of pancreatic lipase inhibition. From this equation, the IC50 value was determined, which indicates the concentration of compound required for 50% inhibition.

Kinetic analysis of enzymatic inhibition

For kinetic evaluation of pancreatic lipase enzyme activity, the substrate 4 -nitrophenyl palmitate was tested at different concentrations ranging from 1.0-10.0 mg. Extracts of *A.fischeri VOIR* and *Fusarium sp.-ALI42R* were evaluated for their ability to inhibit lipase over time at concentrations of 0.5-15.0 mg/mL. Simultaneously, a negative control sample without inhibitor was used for comparison. Similarly, Xenical as a positive control was tested at concentrations of 0.5-15.0 mg/ml. Inhibition constants (K_m) and maximum rate (V_{max}) were obtained from Michaelis-Menten plots, and the mode of inhibition of the enzyme was elucidated using Lineweaver-Burke plots. All parameters and graphical representations were calculated and generated using GraphPad Prism 8.4.3 software. A double inverse plot ($1/V$ vs. $1/[S]$) was constructed to determine the kinetics of lipase inhibition, where V is the reaction rate and $[S]$ is the substrate concentration. The type of inhibition was identified by the change in the parameters V_{max} and K_m , as reflected by the slope angle and the intersection of the lines in the Lineweaver-Burke plot [15]. All analyses were performed in three repetitions.

Results and discussion

In studying the inhibitory properties of various compounds against enzymes, an important aspect is to analyze the effect of inhibitors on the kinetic characteristics of the enzymatic process. This analysis involves the determination of the types of inhibition such as competitive, non-competitive and mixed inhibition and the calculation of relevant kinetic parameters such as Michaelis constant (K_m) and maximum reaction rate (V_{max}). The determination of these parameters provides further insight into the mechanism of action of the inhibitors and their potential efficacy.

Previously, ethyl acetate extracts of *A.fischeri VOIR* and *Fusarium sp.-ALI42R* were found to produce secondary metabolites that significantly inhibit pancreatic lipase activity [16].

The study of the concentration dependence of the inhibitory effect of the extracts showed a dose-dependent nature of inhibition, and the maximum level of inhibition was reached at a concentration of 10 mg/ml (Table 1). The values of half-maximal inhibition (IC50) for *A.fischeri*

VOIR and *Fusarium sp.-AL142R* under the experimental conditions are 20.5 and 20.7 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively, which is at the level of the standard preparation Xenical 20.6 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

Table 1

Effect of extract concentration on the level of PL inhibition

№	Amount of extract, mg	% of PL inhibition		
		Xenical IC50 20.0 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	<i>A.fischeri</i> VOIR IC50 20.0 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	<i>Fusarium sp. - AL142R</i> IC50 20.7 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
1	0.5	21.4	20.4	15.6
2	1.0	58.7	59.3	35.2
3	2.0	60.2	62.5	41.4
4	4.0	64.3	65.7	58.2
5	6.0	74.5	70.5	68.4
6	8.0	85.6	81.2	70.6
7	10.0	92.0	91.5	88.5
8	15.0	90.1	88.9	84.2

Since the nature of the inhibitor's influence on the kinetic characteristics of the enzymatic process is important in assessing the effectiveness of the inhibitory properties of various compounds with respect to any enzymes, we studied the dependence of the enzymatic reaction rate on the concentration of the substrate 4-nitrophenylpalmitate in the presence of endophyte extracts. Figures 1, 2 show the dependence of the hydrolysis rate on the substrate concentration of 4-nitrophenylpalmitate in the presence of extracts of secondary metabolites in Michaelis-Menten and Lineweaver-Berk coordinates.

In competitive and non-competitive inhibition, changes in the values of K_m and V_{max} , respectively, were observed. In non-competitive inhibition, the degree of reversible inhibition depends only on the inhibitor concentration and does not change when the substrate concentration is varied. This indicates that the interaction of the inhibitor with the enzyme occurs at a site important for activity, but not in the active center where the substrate binds, i.e., the affinity of the enzyme for its substrate does not change; the inhibitor affects V_{max} .

Figure 1. Michaelis-Menten curves for the extract of *A.fischeri* VOIR (A), *Fusarium sp. - AL142R* (B) and Xenical (C), (1- in the absence of inhibitor, 2 - in the presence of inhibitor)

Figure 2. Lineweaver-Berk curve for *A.fischeri* VOIR (A), *Fusarium sp.-AL142R* (B) and Xenical extract (C), (1- in the absence of inhibitor, 2 - in the presence of inhibitor)

As can be seen from the data presented in Figure 2, despite the decrease in lipase activity, metabolites of *Fusarium sp.-AL142R* extract do not affect the value of the catalytic constant of lipase. For competitive inhibition at different substrate concentrations, the lines cross at the same point. Competitive inhibitors affect only K_m , but not V_{max} . The lines obtained in the absence and presence of the inhibitor intersect on the ordinate axis. In this case, in the presence of inhibitor compounds, the value of K_m increases 1.5 times and amounts to 16.0 mg/ml in *Fusarium sp.-AL142R*, V_{max} with and without inhibitor is 0.02 mg/min (Table 2). This suggests that the type of inhibition in *Fusarium sp.-AL142R* is competitive.

Table 2

Effect of inhibitor extracts on the catalytic properties of pancreatic lipase

№	Indicators	Without inhibitor	<i>A. fischeri</i> VOIR (non-competitive inhibition)	<i>Fusarium sp.-AL142R</i> (competitive inhibition)	Standard-Xenical (competitive inhibition)
1.	K_m , mg/ml	10.0	10	16.0	25
2.	V_{max} , mg/min	0.02	0.005	0.02	0.02

Non-competitive inhibitors bind to the enzyme in a site different from the active center, which leads to a decrease in the maximum reaction rate (V_{max}). As can be seen from the presented data (Fig.1, 2) the value of V_{max} (on the ordinate axis) in the presence of *A.fischeri* VOIR extract decreases and is 0.005 mg/ml, and without inhibitor is 0.02 mg/min, which indicates the effect of inhibitor on the enzyme activity. Meanwhile, the value of K_m remains constant under non-competitive inhibition because the inhibitor does not affect the binding of substrate to the enzyme. K_m remains 10 mg/ml both in the presence and absence of inhibitor (Table 2). This suggests that the type of inhibition in *A.fischeri* VOIR is non-competitive.

We observed a marked change in the kinetic constants for lipases with the commercial inhibitor Xenical (Fig.1, 2). As can be seen from the data obtained, despite the decrease in lipase activity, Xenical does not affect the value of the catalytic constant. At the same time, the Michaelis constant increases almost 2.5 times and amounts to 25.0 mg/ml (on the abscissa axis). This indicates that the affinity of the inhibitor for the enzyme is higher compared to the substrate and the inhibition of activity is of the competitive type.

It should be noted that reports on the type of inhibitor action in the literature are mainly for plant inhibitors [17]. For example, Shukla et al. (2015) analyzed the inhibitory effects of plant alkaloids on key enzymes of carbohydrate metabolism using double inverse Lineweaver-Burke plots [18]. For endophytic fungi, data on the type of inhibitory action are also available. Zhou and Yuen (2016) characterized the antifungal activity and mechanisms of action of metabolites of endophytic fungi using Lineweaver-Berk coordinates to determine the types of inhibition [19]. Similarly, Wiyakrutta et al (2004) studied the inhibitory effect of compounds isolated from endophytic fungi on enzymatic activity using double inverse plots [20].

The presented data indicate that inhibitor compounds of endophytic fungi are able to influence the kinetic properties of lipase both by a competitive type similar to Xenicals.

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